

TABLE 2—RELATIVE OXIDISING ABILITIES OF ACID CHROMATE AND CHLOROCHROMATE

Solvent	90% Acetone (v/v)	Aqueous solution	86.5% Acetic acid
Equilibrium constant of formation ($K_{\text{ClCrO}_3^-}$)	1.4×10^6	42	1.1×10^6
Relative oxidising capacities ($k_{\text{HCrO}_4^-}/k_{\text{ClCrO}_3^-}$)	20	22	50

in the aqueous medium, it is rather low. As compared to the value of 42 obtained from kinetics for the chlorochromate formation constant in water, a value of 17 has also been found by other methods². The comparative oxidising abilities of acid chromate and chlorochromate listed in Table 2 show that acid chromate is very potent in acetic acid and weak in aqueous medium. Such enhanced oxidising ability of chromium(VI) in media of very high acetic acid content has earlier been attributed to the formation of acetochromate³, $\text{CH}_3\text{COOCrO}_3^-$, the anion here involved with chromium(VI) being the acetate ion. Thus, if the latter is the oxidant species in aqueous acetic acid, both HCrO_4^- and ClCrO_3^- are weaker oxidants than acetochromate. It is also noteworthy that in an aqueous medium, the oxidising abilities of the different chromium(VI) species become less different than in the low polar media.

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Studies on Catalytic Action of Substituted 12-Molybdophosphoric Acid

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FROM a survey of the patent literature, Ohara and Niina¹ stated that the majority of catalysts are heteropoly compounds containing both molybdenum and phosphorous as essential elements. It contains large cluster anions called Keggin units². In its fully oxidised form, a Keggin unit possesses 40 oxygen atoms which are classified into three

bonding types³, i.e. 4-oxygen atoms which are bonded to central P^{5+} (O_p), 24 to 2 Mo^{6+} (O_b), and 12 to only 1 Mo^{6+} (O_t), where the notations denote that oxygen bonded to the central phosphorous O_p , bridging oxygen O_b , and terminal oxygen O_t , respectively.

Heteropoly compounds, such as 12-molybdophosphoric acid ($\text{H}_2\text{PMo}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$) have been used as an acid catalysts (e.g. hydration of propene) and also as oxidation catalysts (e.g. oxidation of methacrolein to methacrylic acid)⁴. Several studies have already been reported concerning the acidity strength measurements of these heteropoly acids, but first order kinetics studies for the hydrolysis of ethyl acetate are not involved.

The purpose of the present investigation is to shed light on how the acidity of 12-molybdophosphoric acid and its catalytic activity can be varied upon partial substitution of H^+ by some alkali metal cations, like Li^+ , Na^+ and K^+ , and Bi^{3+} cations for comparison.

Experimental

12-Molybdophosphoric acid (B.D.H.) was incorporated with the nitrates of Li^+ , Na^+ , K^+ or Bi^{3+} . An aqueous solution containing the required amounts of these cations to form the mono and the bimetal salts with the heteropoly acid was added to a solution of 12-molybdophosphoric acid with vigorous stirring and then evaporated over a water-bath for 24 h to dryness. The produced solids were calcined at 300° for 4 h in air stream.

The ir spectra (KBr) were taken using a Perkin-Elmer 599 B spectrophotometer, in the range 4 000–200 cm^{-1} .

The acidity of the samples was estimated by measuring the liberated amounts of acid produced by the hydrolysis of ethyl acetate. The reaction was carried out in a water thermostat using a 5.0% aqueous solution of ethyl acetate at 60°. The extent of hydrolysis of ethyl acetate was determined by conventional titrimetry with 0.1 N NaOH solution and phenolphthalein as an indicator to measure the concentration of acetic acid liberated in the reaction.

The catalytic activity of the heteropoly compounds were measured via the dehydration reaction of propan-2-ol, it was carried out using a conventional flow reactor. Purified air was used as a carrier gas. The exit feed was analysed chromatographically using a Pye 104 gas chromatograph with a polyethylene glycol (20%) column coated on celite.

Results and Discussion

A series of catalysts having the general formula $\text{M}_x\text{H}_{9-2x}\text{PMo}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$ (where, $\text{M} = \text{Li}^+$, Na^+ , K^+ ; $\text{X} = 1, 2$) was prepared. In addition to this series $\text{Bi}(\text{H}_2\text{PMo}_{12}\text{O}_{40})_3$ and $\text{Bi}_2(\text{HPMo}_{12}\text{O}_{40})_3$ were also prepared. Fig. 1 shows the ir spectra for these catalysts

including the free heteropoly acid. The free acid showed ir bands corresponding to three bonding types of oxygen^{5,6}, i.e. P—O_p (1065 cm⁻¹), Mo—O_t,

Fig. 1. Ir absorption spectra for (a) pure and (b-d) substituted 12-molybdophosphoric acid, $MH_2PMo_{12}O_{40}$ and (e-g) $M_2HPO_{12}O_{40}$, where, $M=K^+$, Li^+ and Na^+ , respectively.

(960 cm⁻¹), and O_b band, respectively, where the suffix p, b and t denotes to oxygen atoms bonded to the central P⁵⁺, to 2 Mo⁶⁺ (bridging), and to only 1 Mo⁶⁺ (terminal), respectively. The ir bands characteristic O_p and O_b are believed to be very sensitive to changes of anion symmetry⁶. Hence, the observed reduction of O_b band strength with salt addition indicates an anion symmetry deterioration with salt formation. On the other hand, the terminal oxygen O_t is bonded to a single Mo ion. The O_t band at 960 cm⁻¹, which is ascribed to a stretching vibration of Mo—O_t, is not sensitive to deterioration of the anion symmetry except a possible band shifting⁷.

The resulted kinetic studies at 60° for the hydrolysis of ethyl acetate in aqueous solution using the free heteropoly acid and its salts show hydrolysis rate (K , min⁻¹) obeyed the first order kinetics (Fig. 2). Accordingly, it can be considered as a measure for the catalyst acidity. These rate constants are cited in Table 1, where the acidity of the catalysts can be expressed as the amount of HCl

Fig. 2. Representative plots of the first order kinetics of ethyl acetate hydrolysis over (a) pure and (b-e) substituted 12-molybdophosphoric acid, $MH_2PMo_{12}O_{40}$, and (f-i) $M_2HPO_{12}O_{40}$, where, $M=K^+$, Li^+ , Na^+ and Bi^{3+} , respectively.

required to attain the same reaction rates over the solid acid catalysts using the equation⁸,

$$K_{HCl} = 3.72 \times 10^{-3} C_{HCl} \quad (1)$$

where, C_{HCl} is concentration of HCl in meq.

The catalytic dehydration products of propan-2-ol over the heteropoly acid catalysts at 150° were mainly propylene, together with negligibly small amount of CO and CO₂ at our catalytic reaction temperature. The percentage conversion of propan-2-ol over the heteropoly acid catalysts, as obtained after a reaction period of 4 h, are listed in Table 1, together with the ethyl acetate hydrolysis rate constants (K , min⁻¹).

TABLE 1—SPECIFIC RATE CONSTANTS OF ETHYL ACETATE HYDROLYSIS, AND % CONVERSION OF PROPAN-2-OL AT 150° TOGETHER WITH ACIDITY OF THE CATALYSTS

Catalyst	Rate constant k $\times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$ g^{-1}	% Conversion of propan-2-ol	Acidity ^a meq. g ⁻¹
$H_2PMo_{12}O_{40}$	2.555	16.20	0.687
$Na_2H_2PMo_{12}O_{40}$	1.797	6.20	0.483
$LiH_2PMo_{12}O_{40}$	1.513	9.50	0.407
$KH_2PMo_{12}O_{40}$	0.958	16.80	0.258
$Na_2H_2PMo_{12}O_{40}$	1.035	8.60	0.294
$Li_2H_2PMo_{12}O_{40}$	0.908	19.50	0.244
$K_2H_2PMo_{12}O_{40}$	0.383	21.60	0.103
$Bi(H_2PMo_{12}O_{40})_3$	2.166	29.17	0.580
$Bi_2(H_2PMo_{12}O_{40})_3$	1.640	30.77	0.441

^a Calculated by applying equation (1).

Fig. 3. shows the way by which the percentage conversion can be graphically represented as a

function of the electronegativity of the substituent cations⁹. The results show the action of H⁺ ions

Fig. 3. Change of specific rate constants of ethyl acetate hydrolysis and % conversion of propan-2-ol⁺ against substituted cation electronegativity using pure and (a) substituted 12-molybdophosphoric acid, $MH_2PMo_{12}O_{40}$, and (b) $M_2HPMo_{12}O_{40}$; where, $M=K^+, Li^+, Na^+$ and Bi^{3+} ions, respectively; * the reaction conditions are: $W/F=0.311$ of $cal\ mol^{-1}\ dm^3\ h^{-1}$, reactant = 4.27% , total flow rate = $224\ ml\ min^{-1}$.

replacement of 12-molybdophosphoric acid by alkali metal cations, such as Li^+, Na^+ and K^+ . It appears that the catalytic properties of the heteropoly acid can be affected according to two factors, the extent of the alkali cations substitution and its electronegativity. From our findings it appears that the latter factor is proportional to the acidity values of the catalysts and is inversely proportional to their catalytic activity (except in case of Bi^{3+} addition) for the dehydration of propan-2-ol.

In order to discuss these results, it is worthy to mention that heteropoly compounds such as $H_2PMo_{12}O_{40}$ and its related compounds, unlike many metal oxides, can interact as catalysts for many reactions by either the bulk or surface molecules¹⁰ or both. Their catalytic activity can be interpreted in connection with the acidity, which is mostly a Bronsted acid in nature¹¹, together with the redox properties of these catalysts. The hydrolysis of ethyl acetate in aqueous solution and the vapor-phase-dehydration of isopropanol over the free and substituted heteropoly acid catalysts provide that the hydrolysis rate obeyed good first order kinetics. This behaviour is similar to the hydrolysis of ethyl acetate in HCl medium which led to a conclusion that Bronsted acidity is responsible for such activity, that is present even in the neutral salts of heteropoly acid¹². Also, a parallelism exists between the acidity decrease and cations electronegativity.

For the series of $M_2H_{3-x}PMo_{12}O_{40}$ (where, $M=K^+, Na^+$, and Li^+ ; $X=1$ or 2), the dehydration order of alcohol decomposition have the sequence $K_2 > Li_2 > K > Na_2 > Li > Na$, where it adopts the nature of acidity decrease.

It is well known that molybdenum ions are the effective cations inside the bulk of these catalysts as well as on the surface. Hence, dehydration of propan-2-ol can be proposed to proceed according to the mechanism,

Since the strength of Bronsted acidity of these heteropoly compounds may be related to the net charge on the outer oxygen atoms where smaller magnitude of negative charge is corresponding to a more mobile proton and hence higher Bronsted acidity¹³. This charge was found to be decreased on increasing the highest oxidation reduction potential of the heteropoly acid¹³. In contrast to this behaviour, the reoxidisability of Mo^V ions was increased. This was gained from the evidence that the nature of electron-donation for Mo^V atoms, formed through the progress of the dehydration process, increases with the lowering of the oxidation-reduction potential. This can give a plausible explanation for the inverse correlation between the acidity and the activity of the heteropoly compounds.

Finally, it was stated by Akimoto *et al.*¹⁴ that the electron affinity of Mo^VI paralleled the electronegativity of the cations added, and the reactivity of Mo^V to oxidation increased with decreasing electronegativity. This means that increase of electronegativity of the cation added will enhance formation of the intermediate (II) and retards the intermediate (III); but from our results, the activity decrease on increasing cation electronegativity deduct that the rate determining step is that step which is accelerated by decreasing the electronegativity or the step in which the intermediate (III) are formed.

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- 1, R=OH
- 2, R=OAc
- 3, R=OTs

4

Surface Reaction on Alumina Catalyst.

Synthesis of 6-Nitrocholesterol-3,5-diene in Dry Media

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BASIC alumina has been successfully employed for the preparation of dienolic esters from β -allenic esters in good yield with high stereospecificity^{1,2}. We report here a simple method for the preparation of 6-nitrocholesterol-3,5-diene (4), a versatile intermediate for the synthesis of steroidal compounds. 3 β -Hydroxy-6-nitrocholesterol-5-ene (1)³ and its 3 β -acetoxy (2)⁴ and 3 β -tosyloxy (3)⁵ analogues when allowed to stand over a column of basic alumina provided 6-nitrocholesterol-3,5-diene (4) in quantitative yield. The elimination of tosyloxy group in 3 seems to be faster as compared to acetoxy or hydroxyl group in 2 and 1, respectively. A probable mechanism of alumina catalysed elimination has been suggested (Scheme 1).

R' = H, Ac, Ts

Scheme 1

10.41; N, 3.38%); $\nu_{\max}$ 1 690 (C=C-C=C-NO₂), 1 515 and 1 350 cm⁻¹ (C-NO₂); δ 6.5d (J 10Hz, C₂-H), 6.0m (C₆-H), 1.0 (C₁₀-CH₃), 0.70 (C₁₈-CH₃), 0.95 and 0.83 (remaining CH₃).

Under similar reaction conditions, 3 β -acetoxy-6-nitrocholesterol-5-ene (2) and 3 β -tosyloxy-6-nitrocholesterol-5-ene (3) afforded 4 in 91 and 93% yields, respectively.

Experimental

IR spectra (nujol) were recorded on Pye-Unicam sp-300 spectrophotometer, and nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian A-60 instrument with Me₄Si as the internal standard. Tlc plates were coated with silica gel. A 20% aqueous solution of perchloric acid was used as spraying agent, anhydrous sodium sulphate used as the drying agent; and weakly basic alumina (200-300 mesh) for column chromatography was used after being dried at 200-300° in muffle furnace.

6-Nitrocholesterol-3,5-diene (4): (a) A solution of 3 β -hydroxy-6-nitrocholesterol-5-ene (1.0 g) dissolved in dry ether (20 ml) was adsorbed over basic alumina (20 g). The residual ether was removed under reduced pressure and the reaction mixture kept at room temperature for 48 h. Elution with ether yielded a semisolid mass which on crystallisation from methanol afforded 6-nitrocholesterol-3,5-diene (4) as yellowish crystals (900 mg, 90%), m.p. 72° (lit⁶ 72-3°) (Found: C, 78.42; H, 10.21; N, 3.25. C₂₇H₄₄NO₂ (M⁺.413) required: C, 78.45; H,

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